

Corporate – Nonprofits Partnerships to Improve Social Innovation and Corporate Social Responsibility

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Abstract

Corporations are under increasing pressure to serve social purposes beyond maximizing shareholder value. One of the best resources for businesses seeking to affect social change meaningfully is through working with, learning from, and partnering with nonprofits. Different approaches have been emerging for nonprofits to inform and support the interests of for-profit businesses in the area of corporate social responsibility (CSR). In particular, collective impact (CI) and its implications for corporate partners; increasing positive community engagement through progressive hiring practices instituted by non-profit organizations (NPOs); fostering innovation within an organizational setting through NPO collaboration; and exploring a hybrid model of non-profit/for-profit business, with an examination of the advantages and disadvantages thereof. In this paper, we review these unique approaches to show how for-profits can learn from nonprofits and *vice versa* when it comes to social innovation and corporate social responsibility.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Social Innovation, Nonprofits, Collective Impact, Triple Bottom-Line

Introduction

For-profits can learn from non-profits, especially with regard to addressing the social and environmental needs of their communities, employees, and society at large. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) refers to activities undertaken by businesses to enhance their value in the community and society and benefit their reputation and brand. “Corporate Social Responsibility is a management concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and interactions with their stakeholders.” UNIDO (2011). For-profits can address their CSR through emerging methods of interaction with nonprofits. To create progressively more robust collaboration, for-profits can build partnerships with nonprofits through an exchange that cultivates innovation, deepens community engagement in organizational business practices, explores organizational hybrid models, and creates Collective Impact. According to a report produced in 2009 by Sabeti there is, “ increasing use of business methods by nonprofits and the growing responsiveness of business to social concerns, and sees “a new class of organizations with the potential for generating immense economic, social, and environmental benefits ... emerging” (Sabeti as cited in Worth, 2019). For-profits can reap the benefits of learning from nonprofits while simultaneously providing them with much-needed expertise. These exchanges are promising, yet expectations, alignment, and integrity must be present from the beginning to accomplish mutual benefits.

Setting the Context Partnership with the private sector has long been used by private foundations (Peterson, Yawson, Sherman, & Johnson Kanda, 2018). The Ford Foundation, the W.K. Kellogg Foundation (WKKF), the Charles Stewart Mott Foundation (Mott), and others have invested several billion dollars in poverty alleviation strategies, many of them tapping business partnerships through Community Development Financial Institutions (CDFIs) and corporate engagement (Peterson et al., 2018).

With growing investments coupled with the more business-oriented mindset of new global philanthropists, it is essential to unleashing the power of business schools to educate future and existing leaders. Many new philanthropists are turning to business schools for help, and many business schools are unprepared to address critical issues involving community partnership, social change, and performance measures that include numbers and nuance required in achieving long-term, sustainable social change (Headwaters Group Philanthropic Services, 2011).

However, even with a growing interest in markets and social change, there are impediments to the perspective that business can be an important partner in addressing the needs of families in deep poverty. There can be a cultural disconnect between corporate decision-makers and the poor. Although business practices based on the triple bottom line (social, environmental, and financial success) that serve the bottom-of-pyramid market abound, many companies are unaware of effective practices or have difficulty maneuvering the needs of low-income people (Headwaters Group Philanthropic Services, 2011). There can be confusion between charity and social programs conducted by business and integrating social concerns into core business practice and making it the responsibility of all managers, not just the province of marketing or community relations departments. Companies' ambitions in addressing poverty may be set too low, and, conversely, their expectations may be too optimistic. Self-regulation, transparency, and sustainability in this work are paramount values.

A review as to why it might be desirable for a nonprofit to join in a venture with a corporate sponsor with a triple bottom line can offer insight. Nonprofits operate in a competitive environment; they compete for gifts from corporations, foundations, and individuals, and government grants. By cultivating an exclusive relationship with a corporate sponsor who has an outstanding reputation for its products or services as well as a willingness to support the nonprofit's vision and mission, a nonprofit organization can establish a robust and advantageous partnership. For instance, the nonprofit does not have to compete for gifts from the corporate sponsor and the need for federal and state grants may be reduced. At times, federal and state grant requirements may pressure nonprofits to target specific communities. This could minimize services, which in turn can widen the poverty gap and collapse the social ladder into the middle class.

The potential benefits for a nonprofit to partner with a for-profit company are significant. Why, then, should a for-profit business develop a partnership with a nonprofit organization and build a triple bottom line of profitability and social return? A for-profit's financial bottom line does not mandate social or environmental returns. A for-profit organization that seeks to become a corporate sponsor must think in terms of business interest and social goals when identifying potential nonprofit partners. It must also consider social goals' sustainability and profitability. For example, the for-profit corporation, Home Depot formed a partnership with the nonprofit KaBOOM!. KaBOOM! builds children's playgrounds. Home Depot sells

building materials, and the business has strong ties with the community. This relationship, therefore, is a good fit. As Worth (2019) states, “it would not be logical for a company that manufactures entertainment products to be a partner with a nonprofit concerned with homelessness.” (p.308).

Another example is Timberland and City Year’s relationship. City Year had a captured audience of people in need. City Year brought Timberland high visibility in communities because volunteers wore the Timberland logo. It was a positive sign of excellent products that supported low-income communities’ education and social advancement. This means low-income children are cultivated with the Timberland’s logo as a symbol of high status. These children, through education, then climb the social ladder and teach their children to value and purchase Timberland products. This is a win-win for City Year and Timberland (Austin et al., 2004).

While nonprofit organizations have routinely implemented alternative strategies to build net assets, in recent years, more are using direct business principles in their programs. Many more have identified the need to use innovative financial planning to diversify their unrestricted income sources – particularly those with a reliance on government – and they are all asking for help in doing so (Illinois Facilities Fund, 2013). For example, in the new world of nonprofit accountability, government and financial donors demand more fiscal responsibility when managing nonprofits with 501(c)(3) IRS status. At the same time, they ask: Are we receiving a return on investment as measured by positive social impact on individuals, families, and communities (Ebrahim and Rangan, 2014, p. 118)? For instance, nonprofits must demonstrate their ability to measure positive social impact before they can receive a grant from United Way. United Way and its partners evaluate the effectiveness of impact strategies, so they can continuously improve. They identify appropriate measures, collect and analyze results, and assess progress toward desired outcomes. Positive social impact can be measured at multiple levels, programs, systems, and communities and may cause United Way and its partners to rethink, change, or adjust strategies, actions, and investments (United Way, 2005, slide 57). A nonprofit organization that is effectively using the triple bottom line has a distinct advantage in procuring funds from sponsors such as the United Way.

Effective measurement of social impact also means that every leader and manager in the nonprofit industry should understand the triple bottom line in order to match the mission statement and vision with social responsibility. Donors’ contributions should be measured to

determine if the funding is actually achieving its intended goals through positive social impact. Additionally, sustainable nonprofits should tie impact goals to financial goals. This effective management of hybrid revenue strategies requires a well-outlined nonprofit business model that links the impact strategy directly with the revenue strategy (Nonprofit Answer Guide, 2014). Long term financial planning begins with an organic and flexible approach that involves trial and error. Even some of the best-made plans can be susceptible to daunting economic downturns.

Nonprofit organizations are searching for alternative ways to mitigate poor revenue streams and funding cuts, which perpetuate competition in their market. A successful mitigation strategy can include collaborations, which are more common due to these financial constraints. Collaborations focus on the beneficial trade-off of a hybrid entity that can diversify its revenue stream and thrive in the competitive nonprofit marketplace. “Management of hybrid strategies can be a challenge. For this reason, different financial goals must be set for different revenue streams” (Nonprofit Answer Guide, 2014). It takes a good leader and manager to make the necessary decisions that can pull resources together in a timely manner for the sake of the organization’s longevity.

For example, there are those opting for a Low-Profit Limited Liability Company (L3C) structure. “The L3C is structured to be able to receive Program Related Investments (PRIs) from foundations, which are grants that enable the foundation to generate a return from the nonprofit entity. Another difference is that while L3Cs are organized as LLCs - they are designated as ‘low-profit organizations’ with specific charitable or educational goals - L3Cs are for-profit in the sense that they can distribute profits, and are nonprofit in the sense that they are organized for charitable purposes” (Sertial, 2012). Ultimately, adequate management of the triple bottom line has leaders and managers rethinking their strategies and organizational structures, developing new decision making and financial models to follow the fiscal health of their organizations, and searching for ways to maximize their potential for social impact and longevity.

Finally, nonprofit organizations often focus on making ends meet today; they must also look to long-term financial sustainability. Effective measurement of the triple bottom line can assist organizations in their analysis of strengths and weaknesses in financial and social aspects. Nonprofits must focus on the long term goals of organizational programs and quality of service to be better equipped to manage this challenge of positive social impact.

Research Questions and Inquiry

We shaped our inquiry around the following questions:

1. How could nonprofits be given a voice and decision-making power within collaborative projects involving business?
2. What can business (For-Profit) learn from nonprofits and *vice versa* to improve social innovation and CSR?

In addressing these questions, we integrate the existing concepts of Innovation through Collaboration, Community Engagement, Hybrid Organization Model, and Collective Impact to highlight examples of for-profits, hybrid social enterprises, and not-for-profits whose goals and outcomes include poverty alleviation.

Innovation through Collaboration

As corporations are pushed to be ever more socially innovative and competitive, it is becoming increasingly expensive to develop social innovation from inside a corporation. There are several reasons why a corporation needs to remain socially innovative, including “for competitive advantage, social legitimacy, or firm survival” (Holmes & Moir, 2007). However, “the locus of innovation lies outside a firm's boundaries and access to a diverse range of external partners within an organization's network is important for driving innovative ideas” (Holmes & Moir, 2007). Partnering with nonprofit organizations has proven to be a useful and socially-responsible answer to innovation creation, regardless of whether the motivation is internally-driven by the corporation or externally-driven by a nonprofit engaging with a corporation to primarily meet the needs of the nonprofit (Holmes & Moir, 2007).

Several vital indicators can lead to a higher probability of collaborative success for both the corporation and the nonprofit. “The willingness of the organization to experiment” is an indicator showing that managers are open to interpreting data as an opportunity and not a threat (Holmes & Moir, 2007). A second indicator is the “innovation orientation of its managers” (Holmes & Moir, 2007), essentially stating that managers must believe that partnering with a nonprofit will benefit both the corporation and the nonprofit; that this partnership is not just an opportunity to give back to the community (Holmes & Moir, 2007). The final indicator is a corporation’s “communicative capacity” (Holmes & Moir, 2007) and “openness to new ideas is widely identified as a critical component of innovation and firms need to have the processes in

place to bridge the boundaries with other organizations” (Holmes & Moir, 2007). As in every collaboration, excellent communication is essential.

Once a collaboration has been established, and the indicators above are showing favorable direction, “research demonstrates the value of an open innovation approach driven by the need to address societal and social issues (rather than those purely economic)” (Holmes & Smart, 2009). This is where the scope is particularly important, as research indicates that outcomes can be drastically different when the scope is defined by the corporation versus the nonprofit approaching a corporation for collaboration. Where the engagement remit had been narrowly defined by the corporate partner at the outset, the opportunity for scope development was limited: the corporate actors appeared to have a clear understanding of why they were engaging with the nonprofit and did not deviate very much from this (Holmes & Smart, 2009). Alternatively,

“where the firm had agreed a broader engagement remit with the NPO at the outset, or indeed, had no agenda for the relationship as the nonprofit had approached the firm, the range of activities was expanded or extended further (often to the surprise of the corporate actors involved), and firm innovations in these cases emerged during the course of the engagement” (Holmes & Smart, 2009).

In conclusion,

“firms with a narrow engagement scope were looking to exploit the skills and resources of the NPO through the collaboration. By contrast, those firms with a broad or an undefined engagement scope were more exploratory in their approach, using the collaboration to search for new innovation opportunities” (Holmes and Smart, 2009).

Collaboration can be an excellent approach to innovation for both corporations and nonprofits alike. Research shows that innovation can occur regardless of which partner initiates the partnership, however, the degree of innovation achieved can be influenced. An example of a successful collaboration includes

“The World Wildlife Fund helping Coca-Cola develop models and create a framework to evaluate tradeoffs between conserving biodiversity and minimizing costs. The partnership has resulted in improved ecological health of seven of the

world's most important freshwater basins while improving Coca-Cola's water efficiency by more than 20%" (Mahmud, 2014).

Once the collaboration is established, alignment of critical indicators, including the willingness of managers to engage, to see the broader purpose, and to create strong communications channels (Holmes and Moir, 2007), can ensure the collaboration is off to a good start. And as the collaboration formalizes, keeping a broad agreement and allowing for an exploratory approach (Holmes and Smart, 2009) can improve the chances of success.

Increasing Community Engagement

Community-engagement is the process of working collaboratively with and through groups of people affiliated by geographic proximity, special interest, or similar situations to address issues affecting the well-being of those people (Osafo & Yawson, 2019). For-profit organizations today have the unique opportunity to increase community engagement efforts in ways that can help target specific community challenges and provide scale to impact society positively. The depth of issues facing communities requires organizations to go beyond their charitable giving and invest in non-traditional ways to improve and strengthen the lives of communities around the world. Expanding a business' community involvement to include efforts to help reduce recidivism through progressive hiring practices is one example of how organizations can go about increasing their social impact. The Salvation Army even in the 1980's had great success with this kind of a program boasting rehabilitation of 80% previously incarcerated people through a strict work program run largely by volunteers (Drucker, 1989). Historically this space has been dominated by non-profits, but there's significant evidence that suggests that for-profits can benefit from and help play a role in reducing recidivism. According to Schnepel (2018) there is a strong correlation between the availability of good jobs in certain sectors and a decrease in recidivism. Schnepel (2018) also found that the existence of low-skill manufacturing and construction employment opportunities at the time of labor market entry is associated with significant reductions in the number of released offenders who return to prison.

Prisons in the United States are built as revolving doors with more than two-thirds of individuals released from prison in California, for example, returning to prison within three years (Schnepel, 2018). The scale of incarceration in the United States is largely driven by the failure of former inmates to reenter society successfully. Released offenders face a number of social, housing, and financial challenges upon leaving prison and an inability to obtain employment are

often cited as one of the most important factors that contribute to recidivism. The National Employment Law Project has reported that approximately 70 million people have some type of arrest or conviction record that prevents them from obtaining jobs, despite relevant knowledge and skillset. Once a potential employer learns of an applicant's criminal history, the chances of that job seeker receiving a call back decreases by 50 percent. The effect is even greater for Black men, where only one in three receives a callback. Although this research showed that employers were hesitant to hire Black people even without criminal records, they became more reluctant to make job offers when they were aware of known criminal history. Conviction records for Black people, then, have significant impacts on one's ability to engage in the labor market (Marek, 2018).

For-profit organizations can look for insights from NPOs in reducing recidivism and apply those lessons learned in meaningful ways in order to solve complex problems facing society. For-profit organizations can institute fair hiring practices like “banning the box,” as more states are starting to do. As of 2016, over one hundred municipalities and twenty-four states have recently adopted a growing fair chance hiring policy called "ban the box," which refers to the commonly used checkbox on job applications inquiring into an applicant's prior criminal record. Ban the box laws mandate that employers remove the question from employment applications asking, "have you ever been convicted for violation of the law other than minor traffic offenses?" Ban the box policies offer fair chances for job opportunities to those with prior criminal records, which encourages rehabilitation, promotes community development, and reduces the recidivism rate (Reed, 2016). One of those states, Hawaii, implemented ban the box law in 1998 and the ban resulted in a substantial decline in repeat offending among criminal defendants being prosecuted for felony crimes in Honolulu County (D'Alessio, Stolzenberg, & Flexon, 2015). The ban the box policies reduce barriers to employment so that people with past criminal involvement - after they have been held accountable and paid their dues - can compete for appropriate work opportunities to support themselves and their families, pay their taxes, and contribute to the economy.

Beyond the hiring opportunities, for-profit organizations must be willing to invest resources in training offenders. California's Last Mile program offers a program called Code 7370, where students are taught computer coding. In 2015, the inmates were provided actual entry-level front-end coding positions from companies outside the prison walls. Programs like

the ones San Quentin prison leads have as low as a 7.1 percent recidivism rate in comparison a 54 percent rate for the rest of the state (Alfaro, 2019). Other nonprofits like The Prison Entrepreneurship Program is a nonprofit organization that connects released felons with executives and entrepreneurs. This re-entry program focuses on teaching leadership and innovation skills. Since the program began in 2004, there have been over 1,300 graduates who began careers with starting wages 60 percent higher than the minimum wage and almost 100 percent are still employed 12 months after their release. Most importantly, the recidivism rate for graduates is below 7 percent, which is far below the national average (Prison Entrepreneurship Program, 2019). Through the examples of non-profits who are committed to hiring and training those who have been incarcerated corporations can contribute to society while not perpetuating the cycles of unemployment and incarceration that exist today.

Figure 1: A model for participation in local economic development

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The challenge of the principles of community engagement, outlined above using recidivism, as an illustration, is putting them into practice (Headwaters, 2011). Some corporate and corporate-nonprofits partnerships have demonstrated the value of successful engagement with the surrounding community. Business and nonprofits can work effectively to engage and give voice to the community whether as targets of charity, the customers or neighbors of a

corporation, or other stakeholders who may be affected by programs and policies. Figure 1 offers an illustration of a model for participation in local economic development. There are many other community-based processes used to engage the community (Osafu & Yawson, 2019).

Hybrid Organization Model

In response to the market demand from the public to focus on corporate social responsibility, hybrid organizations are becoming common. Hybrid organizations are enterprises that design their business models based on the alleviation of a particular social or environmental issue (Haigh, Walker, Bacq, Kickul, 2015). The case for the hybrid model is that it blurs the boundaries of traditional nonprofits and for-profits by incorporating social missions like nonprofits and generating income to accomplish the mission like for-profits. (Haigh & Hoffman 2012).

Committed to doing good business, but also doing good by society, the main objective of hybrid organizations is to increase profitability while concurrently pursuing a social mission. With a two-part bottom line, hybrid organizations have changed the conversation about for-profit and mission-based work. Through careful attention to financial planning and the effective use of technology, nonprofit and hybrid organizations alike can ensure they are prepared to meet the challenges of tomorrow, while continuously building and expanding a base of donors, stewards and volunteers. Thus, a dual-pronged approach serves as the foundation of sustainable organizational operations.

Hybrid organizations can be either for-profit or non-profit. Two examples of this are; Ten Thousand Villages, which is a nonprofit that uses a for-profit retail model to sell goods and provide income to artisans; Seventh Generation, a for-profit, that strives to be the most environmentally responsible cleaning product in the world (Haigh & Hoffman 2012). In defining a legal structure, hybrids can be broken down into three different segments; a for-profit structure that links a strong social mission; a nonprofit structure that earns some or all of its revenue; and a “mixed-entity” structure that associates a for-profit with a nonprofit through ownership, contracts, and donations (Haigh, Kennedy, Walker, 2015).

In addition to these three legal structures, for-profit organizations have begun to see a growing number of business registration categories. These categories have been created to highlight the dual social-economic purposes of the organization. Some of the categories are also valuable to those organizations initially looking to register as a nonprofit. The list of some of

these categories is (dependent on state) Low-Profit Limited Liability Company (L3C) and Benefits LLC, and variations of the corporation, Benefit Corporation, Flexible Purpose Corporation, and Social Purpose Corporation (Haigh et al., 2015).

Notably, the blurring of for and nonprofit sectors has led to more organizations generating more revenue from charitable gifts and business ventures while utilizing business methods in pursuit of their social mission (Worth, 2019). Traditional organizations can leverage hybrid models and strategies not only to extend their responsibility to social and environmental goals or in the policy of their fiscal sustainability practices but also to pioneer their business model. With this being said, organizations may learn how to launch their business models in ways that go above current norms, making their mission profitable, rather than making profit their only mission. Hybrids, as opposed to traditional, consider the integrity of nature a rewarding pursuit and its preservation value that benefits society (Alberti, Garrido, 2017). “Partnerships have become attractive to corporations, some of whom eagerly seek relationships with nonprofits that provide a good fit with their strategic goals. Some engage for-profit marketing firms to identify organizations and negotiate the partnership agreement.” (Worth, 2019, p. 309). Nonprofit and hybrid organizations alike can greatly benefit from establishing, tracking, and reporting on the triple bottom line.

Collective Impact

One of the most sweeping ways for-profits can engage in affecting social change is to partake in coalitions of organizations across sectors in a coordinated effort, capitalizing on the concept of collective impact. The originators of this idea define collective impact as “the commitment of a group of important actors from different sectors to a common agenda for solving a specific social problem” (Kania, Kramer, 2011). “The main thesis underlying the collective impact framework is that while each organization faces a unique set of challenges because of differing levels of operations, differing visions and missions, variances in corporate culture, and the different corporate stories of impacts, there are also crucial commonalities” (Yawson, Peterson & Johnson-Kanda, 2020, p.3).

For-profits engage in philanthropy through charitable donations, but also have many additional resources that can be utilized for social purposes outside the organization. For example, data collection and analysis are something that a large for-profit company may excel at, but it is incredibly challenging for smaller nonprofits to gain competency. By lending their

expertise and some of their employees' time, for-profits can provide other actors with support in critical spaces that would otherwise be impossible to access. In this way, for-profits can use their resources and knowledge to support communities through collective impact to partner across for-profit, nonprofits, government and community organizations to effectively and efficiently promote social good (Kania, Kramer, 2011).

Additionally, corporations are well-positioned to support the creation of coordinating entities within a coalition or community called backbone organizations to maximize collective impact (Easterling, 2013). Backbone organizations are instrumental in building and supporting effective alliances. As Kania and Kramer note,

The expectation that collaboration can occur without a supporting infrastructure is one of the most frequent reasons why it fails. The backbone organization requires a dedicated staff separate from the participating organizations who can plan, manage, and support the initiative through ongoing facilitation, technology, and communications support, data collection and reporting, and handling the myriad logistical and administrative details needed for the initiative to function smoothly” (Kania, Kramer 2011).

Traditionally, corporate philanthropy consists of writing a check or donating some time towards the work of external organizations, often non-profit or public sector. This is top-down philanthropy, in which corporations can support the existing work of others, but are somewhat limited in their ability to impact the way that work is being done. Collective impact is a type of “networked” philanthropy, where individual players with unique skill sets and perspectives come together around a common goal, pooling different kinds of resources as needed to address the more significant cause. For the network to communicate across silos, a backbone organization is required. Backbone organizations can take the form of funder-based, developing a new nonprofit, other existing non-profits, and government (FSG, 2019). An example of a backbone organization is National Fund for Workforce Solutions, which works across sectors and has regional collaboratives to “individuals develop new skills and access a good job, businesses find trained employees, and communities generate prosperity for all” (National Fund for Workforce Solutions, 2019). Successful, profitable corporations know how to communicate and coordinate internally across complex organizational hierarchies. In many ways, the schema used to keep the for-profit corporation working towards the collective mission can be applied externally, to

outside teams, groups, and institutions working towards social causes. While a corporation should not function as a backbone organization itself (backbones need to be independent to function properly), it can work closely with the community in informing and the process of building an effective one.

Conclusion

The demand from consumers that for-profit organizations operate with corporate social responsibility has forced a shift to develop new ways of balancing financial, social, and environmental priorities. For-profits are looking to nonprofits to inform gaps of knowledge and drive innovation through partnership to ensure competitive advantage. They could also learn and internalize community-focused business practices that seek to end injustices such as the cyclical nature of incarceration and unemployment that the Salvation Army has addressed in their hiring practices for over thirty years. Furthermore, hybrid organizations offer a different stake in how businesses can create positivity with NPO's and corporate partners by working together to create a sustainable infusion of social impact principles into modern capitalism. Finally, there has been widespread momentum around collective impact as it establishes a vital shift in addressing significant system issues that require collaboration among all sectors to make real change. It is not prudent or effective for entities to take on collective impact without utilizing backbone organizations to support coalitions.

Through collaboration with nonprofits at varying degrees, for-profits strengthen public perception of their corporate social responsibility and can implement practices that can even aid in profit growth. Ultimately for-profits are confronted with the reality that they must learn from nonprofits who have always had the challenge of balancing financial, social, and environmental responsibilities in their business practices. Some of society's most significant issues will require solutions that require collaboration across sectors and the understanding that financial gain cannot always be a top priority in the pursuit of the greater good.

Private-sector businesses have a unique role to play in solving social challenges—they have the tools, a stake in improving these markets, and collectively access to global capital that significantly exceeds the available pool of foreign aid. Nonprofits can seize this moment and leverage these resources to achieve its goals of improving the situation of the very poor. This paper has identified opportunities for businesses and nonprofits to embrace the notion that business has a stake in improving quality of life among and providing goods and services to the

poor both in developing economies and in the United States. We have also identified ways to learn these lessons together and to scale up and disseminate successful models quickly through multi-sector networks of practice.

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References

- Alberti, F. G., & Varon Garrido, M. A. (2017). Can profit and sustainability goals co-exist? New business models for hybrid firms. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 38(1), 3-13.
doi:10.1108/JBS-12-2015-0124
- Austin, J., Leonard, H., & Quinn, J. (2004) Timberland: commerce and justice. *Harvard Business School*, 9-305-002.
- D'Alessio, S. J., Stolzenberg, L., & Flexon, J. L. (2015). The effect of Hawaii's ban the box law on repeat offending. *American Journal of Criminal Justice*, 40(2), 336.
doi:10.1007/s12103-014-9251-9
- Drucker, P. (1989). What business can learn from nonprofits. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/1989/07/what-business-can-learn-from-nonprofits>
- Easterling, D. (2013). Getting to collective impact: How funders can contribute over the life course of the work. *The Foundation Review*, 5(2), 67. doi:10.9707/1944-5660.1157.
- Haigh, N., & Hoffman, A. J. (2012). Hybrid organizations. *Organizational Dynamics*, 41(2), 126-134. doi:10.1016/j.orgdyn.2012.01.006
- Haigh, N., Kennedy, E. D., & Walker, J. (2015). Hybrid organizations as shape-shifters: Altering legal structure for strategic gain. *California Management Review*, 57(3), 59-82.
doi:10.1525/cm.2015.57.3.59
- Haigh, N., Walker, J., Bacq, S., & Kickul, J. (2015). Hybrid organizations: Origins, strategies, impacts, and implications. *California Management Review*, 57(3), 5-12.
doi:10.1525/cm.2015.57.3.5
- Headwaters Group Philanthropic Services. (2011). *Philanthropy and Private Sector Partnerships: Lessons in Social Change for the 21st Century - Wealth Generation and Family Economic Security in the United States and Latin America*. Chicago, IL: The Kellogg Foundation.
- Holmes, S. and Moir, L. (2007). Developing a conceptual framework to identify corporate innovations through engagement with non-profit stakeholders. *Corporate Governance*, 7(4), 414-422. doi: 10.1108/14720700710820498
- Holmes, S. and Smart, P. (2009). Exploring open innovation practice in firm-nonprofit engagements: a corporate social responsibility perspective. *R&D Management*, 39(4) 394-409. Doi:10.1111/j.1467-9310.2009.00569.x

- Illinois Facilities Fund. (2013). Social Entrepreneurship: The Double Bottom Line. *Capacity Building Digest*, 3, 1–15. Retrieved from http://www.iff.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/cbd_series_3.pdf
- Kania, J. & Kramer, M. (2011). Collective impact. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, 9(1), 36.
- Mahmud, A. (2014, February 27). Beyond charity: three innovative types of business partnerships for nonprofits. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from: <https://www.theguardian.com/sustainable-business/ngo-business-nonprofit-partnerships-gsk-nespresso-wwf-coke>.
- Marek, E. U. (2018). The post-incarceration kitchen: Food-based community organizing and employment after imprisonment. *American Studies*, 57(3), 57-79.
doi:10.1353/ams.2018.0047
- National Fund for Workforce Solutions. (2019). Regional collaboratives. Retrieved from: <https://nationalfund.org/regional-collaboratives/>
- Nonprofit Answer Guide. (2014). Is Non Profit Sustainability a Reality. *Center for Nonprofit Management*. Retrieved from <http://nonprofitanswerguide.org/faq/leadership/is-nonprofit-sustainability-a-reality/>
- Osafo, E., & Yawson, R. M. (2019). The role of HRD in university – community partnership. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 43(5/6), 536–553.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-12-2018-0119>
- Peterson, G., Yawson, R. M., Sherman, J., & Johnson Kanda, I. (2018). A systems model of using the Deliberate Leadership® framework for addressing wicked problems. *International Journal of Business and Systems Research*, 12(3), 262–289.
<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBSR.2018.10010536>
- Prisoner Entrepreneurship Program. (2019). PEP not just a program- a revolution. Retrieved from: <https://www.pep.org/>
- Reed, M. M. (2016). Banning the box in Tennessee: Embracing fair chance hiring policies for ex-offenders. *The University of Memphis Law Review*, 47(1), 391.
- Sabeti, H. (with the Fourth Sector Network Concept Working Group). (2009, September 9). The emerging fourth sector: Executive summary. Washington, DC: Aspen Institute. Retrieved from <http://www.aspeninstitute.org/publications/emerging-fourth-sector-executive-summary>

Schnepel, K. T. (2018). Good jobs and recidivism. *The Economic Journal*, 128(608), 447-469.
doi:10.1111/eoj.12415

UNIDO (2011). Scaling up industrial energy efficiency management across Mexico
<http://www.unido.org/index.php?id=o72054> Accessed 06/13/2011

United Way (2005) Measuring community impact: indicators and methods. *2005 United Way Community Leaders Conference*. PowerPoint presentation. Retrieved from
[http://studio.unitedway.org/CILresources08/files/community%20outcomes/Measuring%20Community%20Impact%202005%20\(2\)%20da.pdf](http://studio.unitedway.org/CILresources08/files/community%20outcomes/Measuring%20Community%20Impact%202005%20(2)%20da.pdf)

Worth, Michael J. (2019) *Nonprofit Management: Principles and Practice*. Thousand Oaks, California. Sage Publications, Inc.

Yawson, R. M., Peterson, G., & Johnson Kanda, I. (2020). Collective Impact: Dialogue at the Interface of the Colliding Systems of Philanthropy. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 16(1), 1 - 21
<https://doi.org/10.1504/WREMSD.2020.105528>